

Mapping research on peace education: the bibliometric analysis for research agenda in the future

Wahyu Nanda Eka Saputra¹, Prima Suci Rohmadheny², Nur Hidayah³, Trikinasih Handayani⁴, Agus Supriyanto¹, Agungbudiprabowo¹

¹Department of Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

²Department of Teacher Education for Early Childhood Education, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

³Department of Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Science Education, Universitas Negeri Malang, Malang, Indonesia

⁴Department of Biology Education, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the trend of scientific publications with the theme of peace education. This study uses bibliometric analysis to describe trends in peace education research and reveal its bibliometric profile. The data was taken from the Scopus database covering 1961 to 2023 with the keywords “peace education” and “violence.” The results of the analysis show that there is a positive trend toward an increase in publications with the theme of peace education. The most prominent country that contributes to peace education-themed publications is the United States. The University of Toronto and the University of Kwazulu-Natal are the most famous universities that publish research results on peace education. The Journal of Peace Education is the favorite journal for publication on the theme of peace education. Vaughn Mitchell John and Johan Galtung are prominent names who have influenced publications on peace education. Potential themes regarding peace education are discussed in this paper. This research contributes to analyzing structure, trends, collaboration opportunities, and research roadmaps as a basis for future research.

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Corresponding Author:

Wahyu Nanda Eka Saputra

Department of Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education,

Universitas Ahmad Dahlan

Banguntapan, Bantul, Yogyakarta, 55166, Indonesia

Email: wahyu.saputra@bk.uad.ac.id.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rational implementation of peace education is to respond to the increasing culture of violence perpetrated by several parties, including students in their teens. Moreover, youth violence in schools is a problem and requires efforts to deal with it until now [1], [2]. Many parties have realized that violence in schools has an impact on mental health [3]–[5], psychological well-being [6], [7], and student’s perceptions of school climate [8], [9]. However, not many teachers understand the volatility of the problem of difficulty that exists in students [10]. At least three things need to be done to deal with student violence in schools: school attachment, teacher support, and parental control over students [11].

The implementation of peace education needs to be recognized as a vital aspect of a school system. At least there are several reasons for the importance of peace education, including as a strategy to build true peace [12]; proven to suppress student violence [13]; cultivating tolerance [14]; and develop conflict

resolution skills [15]. Especially in a country known for its multicultural, vital peace education is implemented in schools [16]. Peace education in several countries is mainly done to respond to problems of violence and conflict that arise [17]–[19].

Peace education has proven successful in creating non-violent environmental conditions. The emergence of a sense of peace within oneself can be an aspect that can suppress students' violent urges [20]. Minimizing violence is one of the conditions desired by school members because it triggers the development of positive perceptions of the school climate [6]. Furthermore, the perception of a good school climate also correlates with the maximum academic performance of students at school [21]. It becomes a challenge for educators to become agents of peace that can accommodate the growth of a culture of peace in schools [22], [23]. Schools can become formal institutions that can promote true peace for every student [24].

The study of the development of peace education is always interesting. Research on peace education using bibliometric analysis has never been carried out before. Only one study reveals four clusters of peace education: civic education, global citizenship, peace education, and democracy education [25]. However, this research does not comprehensively describe peace education research. This research is important because it provides a roadmap for future research. Based on the analysis that has been described, this study aims to describe: i) countries and institutions that have contributed significantly to publications about peace education; ii) journals that publish articles related to peace education; iii) the themes that often appear in publications are peace education; and iv) data of prominent researchers who have contributed significantly to peace education publications.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study uses bibliometric analysis to analyze large amounts of research data published in scientific journals. The examination results will obtain data visualization through research patterns, trends, and metadata. We use the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) model guide [26], [27] to describe a research flow that is simulated from identification, source selection, and screening processes. The PRISMA model in this research is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram

2.2. Data collection tools

We searched research data on peace education in Scopus-indexed journals from 1961 to 2023. Articles published in Scopus-indexed journals were chosen because articles must go through a strict peer-review process to ensure the eligibility of the article to be published. In addition, articles indexed by Scopus also have broad and diverse scientific disciplines, so the data obtained can be more varied. Several Scopus-

indexed publications exist, such as journals, conference proceedings, and books. Scopus is a suitable choice in bibliometric analysis because it can show metadata such as author, institutional, and country-level analysis, co-citation analysis, and research network mapping. We use the keywords “peace education” and “violence” to identify articles that fit the research objectives.

2.3. Data extraction

Relevant article publications according to the research objectives were identified through the Scopus database. Articles published in Scopus indexed journals are of good quality and have gone through a strict review process. A total of 506 articles were selected independently for bibliometric analysis.

2.4. Research procedure

Research goes through a number of stages. First, we formulate the research topic. The topic determined in this research is mapping research on peace education. Second, we set Scopus as a database to search for journal articles that publish the topic of peace education. Scopus was chosen because the articles had gone through a strict peer review process. Third, we analyzed the data through the analysis tools in Scopus and the VOSViewer application. From this bibliometric analysis, a research map on peace education can be obtained which can be the basis for carrying out further research.

2.5. Statistical analysis

VOSViewer application version 1.6.16 is used to perform bibliometric analysis. The application pays special attention to graphical representations that can provide detailed interpretation of bibliometric maps. Furthermore, the analysis in this study is presented using pictures, graphs, and tables. Data is exported to Microsoft Excel for compilation, correction, and selection. Map visualizations are created using the VOSViewer application.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Peace education is a response to many forms of violence in the international world. Through educational settings, peace begins to be built in each student. The awareness of researchers and practitioners in education on the importance of integrating peace education into the curriculum is increasing. This increased awareness is translated into the increasing number of publications on peace education. We obtained Figure 2 from the Scopus database, which describes the number of publications on peace education from year to year. Publications on peace education began in 1961. In the 2000s, the number of publications on peace education began to show a significant increase, and the peak occurred in 2020 to 2023, with the number of publications reaching 35 to 53 articles per year.

Figure 2. Published data from 1954 to 2023 with the number of documents

3.1. The top 10 countries and institutions in peace education publications

Many countries have contributed to publications that contain elements of peace education. Table 1 presents the highest number of publications and citations for the 10 countries in peace education publications. The countries with the highest contributions to publications on peace education are the United States, United Kingdom, Spain, Colombia, Canada, South Africa, Brazil, Israel, Australia, and India. The first publication was made by the author in United States in 1961 [28], Spain in 2009 [29], Colombia in 2016 [30], Canada in 1992 [31], South Africa in 1996 [32], Brazil in 2006 [33], Israel in 2004 [34], Australia in 2007 [35], and India [36]. Apart from having the most total publications, the United States also has the most total citations. “Twenty-five years of peace research: 10 challenges and some responses” by Galtung is the article with the most total citations, reaching 200 [37].

In the next section, we show co-authorship and country analyses with at least five documents per country. Based on these criteria, it was found that 22 out of 89 countries met the specified criteria. The results of the analysis show that there are at least six research clusters as shown in Figure 3. The first cluster is India, Italy, Nigeria, Norway, South Africa, and Sweden represented in red. The second cluster is Brazil, Canada, Colombia, Mexico, and Spain represented in green. The third cluster is Australia, the Netherlands, and the Russian Federation represented in blue. The fourth cluster is Indonesia, Japan, and Malaysia represented in yellow. The fifth cluster is Israel, South Korea, and the United Kingdom represented in purple. Finally, the sixth cluster is Turkey and the United States represented by the color toska.

Table 2 describes the 10 universities with the highest contribution to publications about peace education. The University of Toronto and the University of Kwazulu-Natal are the affiliates with the highest contributions in publications about peace education, with 10 documents. Meanwhile, the University of Haifa is the affiliate with the most total citations, reaching 278.

Based on Table 2, it can be concluded that some publications that contribute to peace education are carried out in the field of social sciences. It becomes interesting to study more deeply because many studies on peace education link it to the role of the teacher [38]–[40]. The teacher is one aspect that determines the success of the implementation of peace education. Even a teacher educating students' about peace requires many attributes, such as compassion, sincerity, guiding a good attitude, behaving according to his knowledge, empathy, and tolerance [23]. Attributes as an educator of peace have proven to be an important component in his success in building a culture of peace through schools. Furthermore, Figure 4 presents an overview of the co-authorship network of most contributive organizations.

Table 1. Top 10 countries in publication and citation about peace education

No	Country	Total publication	Total citation
1	United States	124	1,869
2	United Kingdom	50	524
3	Spain	34	152
4	Colombia	31	43
5	Canada	30	171
6	South Africa	26	103
7	Brazil	19	54
8	Israel	16	338
9	Australia	14	156
10	India	13	32

Figure 3. Co-authorship network of the countries with the highest contributions

Table 2. Top 10 affiliations in publications and citations about peace education

No	Affiliation	Total publication	Total citation
1	University of Toronto	10	93
2	University of Kwazulu-Natal	10	17
3	University of Cambridge	9	92
4	University of Haifa	6	278
5	Queen's University Belfast	6	49
6	Universidad de Granada	5	25
7	Columbia University	5	25
8	Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia	4	0
9	University of Pennsylvania	4	21
10	University of Otago	4	25

Figure 4. Co-authorship network of most contributive organizations

Based on Figure 4, can be analyzed affiliated clusters that have publications about peace education. The results of the analysis in Figure 4 show that there are 16 clusters: i) American University and George Washington are represented in red; ii) the University of Cambridge and Keimyung University are represented in green; iii) Universidad of Valladolid and Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Honduras are represented in blue; iv) the University of Haifa is represented in yellow; v) the University of Benin is represented in purple; vi) McGill University is represented in orange; vii) the University of Otago is represented in brown; viii) New York University is represented in light purple; ix) University of Toronto is represented in pink; x) University of Kwazulu-Natal is represented in light green; xi) Universidad de Granada is represented in gray; xii) light yellow citizens represent Universidad de Malaga; xiii) Universidad Simon Bolivar is represented in light gray; and xiv) the University of Pennsylvania is represented in toska.

Peace educators move to build a culture of peace through school settings. They become agents of peace whose job is to suppress a culture of violence in schools [41], [42]. School is one of the potential institutions to build true peace in every student. At school, students learn peaceful content that can be taken from various sources, for example, local wisdom [17], local figures [19], and games [43]. Some studies recommend integrating peace education into the school curriculum [44]–[46]. The development of a peaceful dimension in students correlates with reduced cases of violence against individuals [20].

3.2. The top 10 journals publishing articles related to peace education

This section describes the journal used for publication on peace education. The most published papers related to peace education are in the Journal of Peace Education. If identified more deeply, almost all journals have a scope in the field of social sciences, especially education. Meanwhile, the Journal of Peace Research ranks first in total citations (N=408) and the SCImago Journal Rank (SJR=2.44). Table 3 presents the journals that contribute most to publications about peace education.

Table 3 explains that the tendency of publications about peace education is focused on the scope of social sciences, especially education. One of the reasons researchers took this step is that the study of building peace is inseparable from educational aspects [47], [48]. Through education, individuals can learn to achieve peace of mind, which can mediate peace in facing several problems in their lives [49]. As proof, the Journal of Peace Education ranks first as the journal that can have the most documents, namely 45 papers. Scope Journal of Peace Education researches peace education, theory, curriculum and pedagogy.

Table 3. Top 10 of journals by total publications, citations, and SCImago Journal Rank

No	Source	Documents	Citations	SJR
1	Journal of Peace Education	45	334	0.346
2	Peace and Conflict	17	186	0.393
3	Journal of Peace Research	7	408	2.444
4	Journal of Aggression, Conflict and Peace Research	6	14	0.246
5	International Review of Education	5	27	0.859
6	Peace Review	5	6	0.149
7	Educational Philosophy and Theory	4	58	0.804
8	Ensaio	4	15	0.358
9	Religious Education	4	6	0.330
10	Research in Comparative and International Education	4	24	0.587

3.3. Trends in publication themes on peace education

Trends in publication themes are used to understand the direction of research on peace education. The results of the publication trend analysis can be used as an opportunity to find novelty in research on peace education. Figure 5 presents a description of keywords that appear in peace education publications. The analysis is based on author keywords and uses co-occurrence analysis with a minimum occurrence of 5 of the 1,294 that appear, and 47 keywords met the threshold.

Figure 5. Co-occurrence network of study themes based on author keywords

The analysis results in Figure 5 show six clusters based on author keywords. Of the six clusters, there are at least four main clusters highlighted, namely i) conflict transformation, critical peace education, curriculum, non-violence, peace cultural, peace education, peacebuilding, positive peace, school violence, teacher education, teacher, and women as shown in red; ii) citizenship, communication, cultural of peace, democracy, diversity, education, education for peace, higher education, human rights, reconciliation, social justice, sustainable development, and violence prevention; as shown in green; iii) children, conflict, Lebanon, poverty, violence, and youth as shown in blue; and iv) citizenship education, Colombia, conflict resolution, identity, memory, and war as shown in tosca color.

Several keywords in these clusters reveal that peace education is part of the curriculum that aims to suppress violence, maintain peace, and build a culture of peace. Figure 5 shows that conflict transformation, critical peace education, curriculum, non-violence, peace culture, peacebuilding, positive peace, school violence, and teacher education are connected with peace education. So it can be understood that peace education suppresses violence [32], peacekeeping [50], and builds a culture of peace [51] through an integration into the curriculum carried out by teachers [52]. Figure 5 describes the frequency of co-occurrence of a keyword with other keywords. Peace education as a keyword shows the highest number of connections ($n=36$), followed by peace ($n=34$), education ($n=32$), peace ($n=36$), and violence ($n=30$).

The following analysis is based on index keyword generalizations used in indexing standards. This analysis considers the occurrence of at least 5 of 923 keywords, and 48 keywords met the threshold. Figure 6, as a whole, presents five clusters. Still, at least there are two important clusters: i) violence (marked in red), which includes the keywords adolescent, adult, aggression, child, conflict, curriculum, prevention and control, program development, program evaluation, school, social behavior, and social status; and ii) education marked in blue which includes the keywords conflict management, learning, peace process, peacekeeping, perception, political violence, social conflict, student, and young population.

Overlay visualization analysis in the next analysis aims to observe when keyword trends emerge. Figure 7 presents the unit of analysis of all indices used with the number of occurrences of overlay 5 of 2,044 keywords, and 105 keywords met the thresholds. The results of the analysis reveal the following six clusters: i) the average number of publications made in 2017 includes keywords such as peace education, conflict resolution, culture of peace, education for peace, peace, non-violence, school violence, and peacebuilding; ii) publications which on average were made in 2015 covering keywords such as education, post-conflict, post war, peace process, peacekeeping, social conflict, and young population; iii) the average publication was made in 2014 covering keywords such as violence, aggression, attitude, empathy, terrorism, mental health, and political conflict; iv) the average publication was made in 2007 covering keywords such as human rights,

create conflict can be suppressed from the start [15], [59], [60]. The nature of peace shows the psychological, social, political, ethical, and spiritual conditions expressed constructively in intrapersonal, interpersonal, intergroup, international, and global human life [61]. Peace education has become an international agenda to create citizens who can act as agents of global justice in fighting arbitrary power and are a means of realizing just peace [62]. Peace education is recommended to be integrated into the school curriculum, the content of which is one or more aspects of peace based on the phenomenon of peace in the field [45], [46], [61].

3.4. Top 10 authors' contributions to publications related to peace education

The author has contributed to publications related to peace education according to his field of knowledge. Total publication abbreviated TP and total citation abbreviated TC. Table 4 describes the 10 authors who have the most publications on peace education, namely John (TP=6 and TC 7), Kester (TP=5 and TC 93), Bickmore (TP=4 and TC 104), Cremin (TP=3 and TC 109), Harber (TP=3 and TC 36), Lauritzen (TP=3 and TC 28), Salomon (TP=3 and TC 212), Standish (TP=3 and TC 16), Ahmed (TP=2 and TC 5), and Benvrovato (TP=2 and TC 10). Solomon is the author with the most total citations, followed by Cremin and Bickmore.

If observed, the total publication data is not fully proportional to the total citations. The total number of publications from the top 10 authors ranges from 2 to 6 papers. At the same time, the total citations range from 5 to 212 times per author. Destination journals that are not yet included in the high-impact category are one of the reasons for the lack of impact of a publication on other publications. In general, the analysis results in this section focus on the contributions of each author on the theme of peace education. The papers from the authors become one of the foundations for further research, especially as a reference for researchers in their fields. The visualization of Table 4 is described in Figure 8.

Table 4. The top 10 authors contributing to peace education publication

No	Author	Affiliation	TP	TC
1	Vaughn Mitchell John	University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa	6	7
2	Kevin Kester	Seoul National University, Seoul, South Korea	5	93
3	Kathy Bickmore	University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada	4	104
4	Hilary Cremin	University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom	3	109
5	Clive Harber	University of Birmingham, Birmingham, United Kingdom	3	36
6	Solvor Mjøberg Lauritzen	Det Teologiske Menighetsfakultet, Oslo, Norway	3	28
7	Gavriel Salomon	Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem, Israel	3	212
8	Katerina Standish	University of Otago, Dunedin, New Zealand	3	16
9	Johan Galtung	Universitetet i Oslo, Oslo, Norway	2	200
10	Denise Benvrovato	University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa	2	10

Figure 8. Bibliographic coupling analysis of the authors

This study also used co-citation analysis with the unit of analysis cited references. The minimum citation threshold is 5 of the 19,123 references cited, resulting in 63 references meeting the threshold. Figure 9 presents a visualization of co-citation analysis with units of analysis cited references. Data analysis shows that there are five clusters. Overall, two papers from Galtung are categorized as publications with the highest total citations. The first paper was cited 21 times [63], and the second 17 times [64]. Next, Figure 9

also explains that papers from Galtung are categorized as publications that have the highest link strength first (N=80) [63] and second (N=64) [64]. The description of the data analysis shows that Galtung is the most influential author in publications on the theme of peace education.

Finally, we conducted a co-citation analysis using the unit of analysis of cited authors. Figure 10 is a visualization of the analysis results with a minimum criterion of 15 citations from 18,953 authors, and the data obtained by 76 authors meets the threshold. Figure 10 shows that there are seven clusters marked with red, green, blue, yellow, purple, turquoise, and orange. Figure 10 combines more than 15 author citations from metadata extracted by VOSviewer. The top 10 authors are Galtung, Bar-Tal, Zembylas, Cairns, Harris, Davies, Salomon, Bekerman, Smith, and Reardon.

Figure 9. Co-citation analysis of cited references

Figure 10. Co-citation analysis of cited authors

Observing the author’s contribution, not always an author with many documents in the Scopus database, also greatly impacts peace education publications. Vaughn Mitchell John, is the author who has the most documents in the Scopus database, but other authors do not cite the articles. The resulting minimal impact allows the authors not to publish in leading journals. Moreover, authors have the satisfaction and tendency to use papers from reputable journals as the basis for their research [65]. In several developing countries, there is an awareness and need for novice researchers to select journals [66]. These conditions contribute to the magnitude of the impact of a paper when it is published in a leading journal. The condition is different from the paper published by Johan Galtung. Although not many documents are in the Scopus

database, they have a big impact. The analysis shows that his research results are a basis for other studies. Galtung is known as a figure who promotes research on peace [67]. Apart from producing works in papers published in Scopus-indexed journals, Galtung is also an active figure in producing books that carry the theme of peace [68]–[70]. The results of this analysis have implications for the urge to select reputable journals as a place to publish research results.

4. CONCLUSION

Peace education aims to support the transformation of human life towards a peaceful condition, both self, social, and environment. Peace education can be integrated with the school curriculum to educate students with peace content. The importance of peace education has implications for publications showing an increase. The United States is a country that has the highest contribution to publications about peace education. The University of Toronto and the University of Kwazulu-Natal are the two universities that have contributed the most to publications on peace education. For journals, the first position contributing to the theme of peace education is the Journal of Peace Education. Publication themes related to peace education, such as peace, education, violence, peacekeeping, peacebuilding, and conflict, provide valuable insights to guide future research. Next to the prominent author aspect, John has the most documents on Scopus, and Galtung has the most influence on Scopus. This paper explains research information on peace education based on the Scopus database from 1961 to 2023. Therefore, future research aims to further explore peace education by considering other variables that have not been raised before. This research has implications for the discovery of new topics in research that raises the theme of peace education, where research contributes to scientific development and implementation of peace education.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. M. Devries, J. C. Child, E. Allen, E. Walakira, J. Parkes, and D. Naker, "School violence, mental health, and educational performance in Uganda," *Pediatrics*, vol. 133, no. 1, pp. e129–e137, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1542/peds.2013-2007.
- [2] E. O. Olsen, L. Kann, A. Vivolo-Kantor, S. Kinchen, and T. McManus, "School violence and bullying among sexual minority high school students, 2009-2011," *Journal of Adolescent Health*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 432–438, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.jadohealth.2014.03.002.
- [3] K. Chau *et al.*, "Association between cumulating substances use and cumulating several school, violence and mental health difficulties in early adolescents," *Psychiatry Research*, vol. 280, p. 112480, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2019.112480.
- [4] E. Duru and M. Balkis, "Exposure to school violence at school and mental health of victimized adolescents: the mediation role of social support," *Child Abuse & Neglect*, vol. 76, pp. 342–352, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.11.016.
- [5] M. Quinlan-Davidson, L. Kiss, D. Devakumar, M. Cortina-Borja, M. Eisner, and M. F. T. Peres, "The role of social support in reducing the impact of violence on adolescents' mental health in São Paulo, Brazil," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 16, no. 10, p. e0258036, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0258036.
- [6] J. J. Varela, D. Sirlopú, R. Melipillán, D. Espelage, J. Green, and J. Guzmán, "Exploring the influence school climate on the relationship between school violence and adolescent subjective well-being," *Child Indicators Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 2095–2110, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s12187-019-09631-9.
- [7] J. J. Varela, P. A. Sánchez, F. Aguayo, C. González, J. Alfaro, and P. de Tezanos-Pinto, "Gender attitudes, school violence and well-being among Chilean adolescents," *Current Psychology*, vol. 42, no. 17, pp. 14107–14121, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s12144-021-02637-z.
- [8] R. Benbenishty, R. A. Astor, I. Roziner, and S. L. Wrabel, "Testing the causal links between school climate, school violence, and school academic performance: a cross-lagged panel autoregressive model," *Educational Researcher*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 197–206, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.3102/0013189X16644603.
- [9] H. Moore, R. A. Astor, and R. Benbenishty, "Role of school-climate in school-based violence among homeless and nonhomeless students: individual-and school-level analysis," *Child Abuse & Neglect*, vol. 102, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2020.104378.
- [10] L. L. Finley, "Teachers' perceptions of school violence issues: a case study," *Journal of School Violence*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 51–66, Jul. 2003, doi: 10.1300/J202v02n02_04.
- [11] A. Frey, V. Ruchkin, A. Martin, and M. Schwab-Stone, "Adolescents in transition: school and family characteristics in the development of violent behaviors entering high school," *Child Psychiatry and Human Development*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 1–13, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1007/s10578-008-0105-x.
- [12] S. Hymel and L. Darwich, "Building peace through education," *Journal of Peace Education*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 345–357, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1080/17400201.2018.1535475.
- [13] C. Harber and N. Sakade, "Schooling for violence and peace: how does peace education differ from 'normal' schooling?" *Journal of Peace Education*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 171–187, Sep. 2009, doi: 10.1080/17400200903086599.
- [14] S. S. Tanyel and F. S. Ş. Kiralp, "Tolerance for sustainable peace culture in a divided society: the effect of peace education on tolerance tendency and human values," *Social Indicators Research*, vol. 156, no. 1, pp. 223–246, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11205-021-02630-w.

- [15] M. R. van Slyck, "Peace education and conflict resolution curricula for middle school students," *Scholarly Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 184–194, May 2019, doi: 10.32474/SJPBS.2019.02.000138.
- [16] M. Lue and K. B. Riyanto, "Multicultural social peaceful education through social guidance and counseling services in development of industrial revolution 4.0," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Seminar on Guidance and Counseling 2019 (ISGC 2019)*, 2020, pp. 241–245, doi: 10.2991/assehr.k.200814.052.
- [17] Purwadi *et al.*, "Peace guidance based on the perspective of Markesot: acceptability and effectiveness of reducing student aggressiveness," *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 213–221, 2022, doi: 10.47750/pegegog.12.01.22.
- [18] W. N. E. Saputra *et al.*, "Peace counseling approach (PCA) to reduce negative aggressive behavior of students," *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 631–637, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.13189/ujer.2020.080236.
- [19] W. N. E. Saputra, N. Hidayah, M. Ramli, and A. Atmoko, "Social sensitization with the teachings of KH Ahmad Dahlan as a counselor strategy to create peace in school: a systematic literature review," *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 135–144, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.47750/pegegog.13.01.16.
- [20] W. N. E. Saputra, A. Supriyanto, P. S. Rohmadheny, B. Astuti, Y. Ayriza, and S. Adiputra, "The effect of negative peace in mind to aggressive behavior of students in Indonesia," *European Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 485–496, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.12973/eu-jer.10.1.485.
- [21] W. N. E. Saputra, A. Supriyanto, B. Astuti, Y. Ayriza, and S. Adiputra, "The effect of student perception of negative school climate on poor academic performance of students in Indonesia," *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 279–291, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.26803/ijlter.19.2.17.
- [22] H. Cremin, "An autoethnography of a peace educator: deepening reflections on research, practice and the field," *Emotion, Space and Society*, vol. 28, pp. 1–8, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.emospa.2018.05.001.
- [23] Purwadi, W. N. E. Saputra, R. R. S. Sudaryani, and P. S. Rohmadheny, "The attributes of peace educators from Sang Pencerah, the biography of KH Ahmad Dahlan: a hermeneutic study," *HTS Teologiese Studies/Theological Studies*, vol. 78, no. 4, pp. 1–8, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.4102/hts.v78i4.7714.
- [24] Y. Namer, L. Wandschneider, J. Middleton, N. Davidovitch, and O. Razum, "How can schools of public health actively promote peace?" *Public Health Reviews*, vol. 42, p. 1604459, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3389/phrs.2021.1604459.
- [25] Ö. F. Sönmez, "Bibliometric analysis of educational research articles published in the field of social study education based on web of science database," *Participatory Educational Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 216–229, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.17275/per.20.30.7.2.
- [26] D. Moher, A. Liberati, J. Tetzlaff, and D. G. Altman, "Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement," *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, vol. 62, no. 10, pp. 1006–1012, Oct. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2009.06.005.
- [27] M. J. Page *et al.*, "The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews," *International Journal of Surgery*, vol. 88, p. 105906, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijso.2021.105906.
- [28] M. Bentley, "Conflict resolution in schools: an explosion of ideas," *Pastoral Care in Education*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 3–6, Jun. 1996, doi: 10.1080/02643949609470958.
- [29] M. Garaigordobil, C. Maganto, J. I. Pérez, and E. Sansinenea, "Gender differences in socioemotional factors during adolescence and effects of a violence prevention program," *Journal of Adolescent Health*, vol. 44, no. 5, pp. 468–477, May 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.jadohealth.2008.09.014.
- [30] J. L. B. Morales, "Conflict, religion and religious education in Colombia," *Theologica Xaveriana*, vol. 66, no. 181, pp. 207–237, 2016.
- [31] J. M. Kirman and K. Briner, "Peace education: a classroom project to end the Iran-Iraq war—a prelude to the gulf war," *Gifted Education International*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 49–54, Jan. 1992, doi: 10.1177/026142949200800111.
- [32] C. Harber, "Educational violence and education for peace in Africa," in *Peace Education in a Postmodern World*, I. M. Harris, Ed. London: Routledge, 1996, pp. 151–169.
- [33] L. K. de Souza, T. M. Sperb, S. McCarthy, and A. M. B. Biaggio, "Brazilian children's conceptions of peace, war, and violence," *Peace and Conflict: Journal of Peace Psychology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 49–63, Mar. 2006, doi: 10.1207/s15327949pac1201_4.
- [34] G. Salomon, "Does peace education make a difference in the context of an intractable conflict?" *Peace and Conflict: Journal of Peace Psychology*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 257–274, Sep. 2004, doi: 10.1207/s15327949pac1003_3.
- [35] M. Branagan, "The last laugh: humour in community activism," *Community Development Journal*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 470–481, Sep. 2007, doi: 10.1093/cdj/bsm037.
- [36] D. T. Alabi, "Religious conflicts in Northern Nigeria: a critical analysis," *India Quarterly: A Journal of International Affairs*, vol. 58, no. 3–4, pp. 273–302, Jul. 2002, doi: 10.1177/097492840205800311.
- [37] J. Galtung, "Twenty-five years of peace research: ten challenges and some responses," *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 141–158, Jun. 1985, doi: 10.1177/002234338502200205.
- [38] G. Gursel-Bilgin, O. Erden-Basaran, and D. J. Flinders, "Turkish pre-service teachers' understandings of war, peace, and peace education," *International Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 117, p. 102112, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijer.2022.102112.
- [39] A. Kaur, "Peace, violence & social distance: ethnography of an elite school in India," *Cogent Education*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 2158674, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1080/2331186X.2022.2158674.
- [40] P. L. Mantilla-Blanco, "We think we're far from conflict, but that's not true": peace building and remembrance through memory sites in Colombia," *Comparative Education Review*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 78–99, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1086/722801.
- [41] A. Halai and N. Durrani, "Teachers as agents of peace? Exploring teacher agency in social cohesion in Pakistan," *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 535–552, 2018, doi: 10.1080/03057925.2017.1322491.
- [42] M. Novelli and Y. Sayed, "Teachers as agents of sustainable peace, social cohesion and development: theory, practice & evidence," *Education as Change*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 15–37, 2016, doi: 10.17159/1947-9417/2016/1486.
- [43] L. Anggraeni, I. Affandi, D. Wahyudin, S. T. Paramitha, and M. G. Ramadhan, "Optimization of the board game as a platform for the concept of peace education: a survey method study," *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science and Technology*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 494–511, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.46328/ijemst.2292.
- [44] J. Lewsader and J. A. Myers-Walls, "Developmentally appropriate peace education curricula," *Journal of Peace Education*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1–14, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1080/17400201.2016.1228527.
- [45] D. Wahyudin, "Peace education curriculum in the context of education sustainable development (ESD)," *Journal of Sustainable Development Education and Research*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 21–32, May 2018, doi: 10.17509/jsder.v2i1.12354.
- [46] D. Wahyudin, T. Ruhimat, L. Anggraeni, and Y. Rahmawati, "Content analyses on peace education on curriculum 2013 in junior secondary schools in Indonesia," in *Borderless Education as a Challenge in the 5.0 Society*, 1st ed., A. G. Abdullah, V. Adriany, and C. U. Abdullah, Eds. London: Routledge, 2020, pp. 93–99, doi: 10.1201/9781003107279-20.

- [47] K. Bickmore, "Policies and programming for safer schools: are 'anti-bullying' approaches impeding education for peacebuilding?" *Educational Policy*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 648–687, Jul. 2011, doi: 10.1177/0895904810374849.
- [48] C. S. Ellison, "The role of education in peacebuilding: an analysis of five change theories in Sierra Leone," *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 186–207, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.1080/03057925.2012.734138.
- [49] A. Yemenici, "Peace education: training for an evolved consciousness of non-violence," *All Azimuth: A Journal of Foreign Policy and Peace*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 5–25, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.20991/allazimuth.167340.
- [50] A. D. B. Cook, "Southeast Asian perspectives on UN peacekeeping: Indonesia and Malaysia," *Journal of International Peacekeeping*, vol. 18, no. 3–4, pp. 154–174, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1163/9789004322059_004.
- [51] R. Setiadi, S. Kartadinata, Ilfiandra, and A. Nakaya, "A peace pedagogy model for the development of peace culture in an education setting," *The Open Psychology Journal*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 182–189, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.2174/1874350101710010182.
- [52] Z. Bekerman and M. Zembylas, "Some reflections on the links between teacher education and peace education: interrogating the ontology of normative epistemological premises," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 41, pp. 52–59, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2014.03.002.
- [53] K. Kester and H. Cremin, "Peace education and peace education research: toward a concept of poststructural violence and second-order reflexivity," *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, vol. 49, no. 14, pp. 1415–1427, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1080/00131857.2017.1313715.
- [54] A. Kohli *et al.*, "Family and community driven response to intimate partner violence in post-conflict settings," *Social Science & Medicine*, vol. 146, pp. 276–284, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2015.10.011.
- [55] K. Ide, "Peace education, domestic tranquility, and democracy: the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear disaster as domestic violence," *Ethics and Education*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 102–112, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1080/17449642.2014.890292.
- [56] M. Z. Tadjoeddin and S. M. Murshed, "Socio-economic determinants of everyday violence in Indonesia: an empirical investigation of Javanese Districts, 1994–2003," *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 689–709, Nov. 2007, doi: 10.1177/0022343307082063.
- [57] R. B. Lopes and C. A. Gomes, "Peace in the classroom as a condition for school success: what does the literature reveal?" *Ensaio: Avaliação e Políticas Públicas em Educação*, vol. 20, no. 75, pp. 261–282, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1590/S0104-40362012000200003.
- [58] D. Bentrovato and M. Nissanka, "Teaching peace in the midst of civil war: tensions between global and local discourses in Sri Lankan civics textbooks," *Global Change, Peace & Security*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 353–372, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1080/14781158.2018.1505716.
- [59] I. M. Harris, "Peace education theory," *Journal of Peace Education*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 5–20, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1080/1740020032000178276.
- [60] V. Tinker, "Peace education as a post-conflict peacebuilding tool," *All Azimuth: A Journal of Foreign Policy and Peace*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 27–42, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.20991/allazimuth.167339.
- [61] H. B. Danesh, "Towards an integrative theory of peace education," *Journal of Peace Education*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 55–78, Mar. 2006, doi: 10.1080/17400200500532151.
- [62] D. T. Snauwaert, "The peace education imperative: a democratic rationale for peace education as a civic duty," *Journal of Peace Education*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 48–60, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1080/17400201.2020.1713068.
- [63] J. Galtung, "Cultural violence," *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 291–305, Aug. 1990, doi: 10.1177/0022343390027003005.
- [64] J. Galtung, "Violence, peace, and peace research," *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 167–191, Sep. 1969, doi: 10.1177/002234336900600301.
- [65] S. Helm, I. Gamefeld, and J. Tolsdorf, "Perceived corporate reputation and consumer satisfaction - an experimental exploration of causal relationships," *Australasian Marketing Journal*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 69–74, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.ausmj.2009.05.003.
- [66] S. Kurt, "Why do authors publish in predatory journals?" *Learned Publishing*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 141–147, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1002/leap.1150.
- [67] T. Tilahun, "Johan Galtung's concept of positive and negative peace in the contemporary Ethiopia: an appraisal," *International Journal of Political Science and Development*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 251–258, 2015, doi: 10.14662/IJPSD2015.033.
- [68] A. Björkdahl and S. Kappler, *Peacebuilding and spatial transformation: peace, space and place*, 1st ed. London: Routledge, 2017, doi: 10.4324/9781315684529.
- [69] J. Galtung, "Peace, conflict, and violence 1," in *Conflict, Peace, Security and Development*, 1st ed., H. Hintjens and D. Zarkov, Eds. London: Routledge, 2014, pp. 25–38.
- [70] J. Galtung, "Peace studies: a ten point primer," in *Peace Studies in the Chinese Century*, 1st ed., A. Hunter, Ed. London: Routledge, 2017, pp. 15–20, doi: 10.4324/9781315247229-2.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Wahyu Nanda Eka Saputra is a Ph.D. and Lecturer, Department of Guidance and Counseling, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Indonesia. His research focuses on peace education, strategy of counseling intervention, counseling based on local wisdom, and counseling based on creative art. He can be contacted at email: wahyu.saputra@bk.uad.ac.id.

Prima Suci Rohmadheny is an Assistant Professor of Education Science and Teacher Training Faculty, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan (UAD), Indonesia. She was graduated her bachelor degree in Universitas Negeri Jakarta and her master degree from Universitas Negeri Jakarta at the same field, Early Childhood Education. She was joined as a lecturer in Universitas Ahmad Dahlan since 2017. She experienced in doing research, giving community services, assessing ECE unit, and so forth. Her research interest is regarding early childhood education teacher's and pre-service teacher's pedagogic competence: learning assessment, teaching and learning strategy. She can be contacted at: prim.rohmadheny@pgpud.uad.a.id.

Nur Hidayah is a professor and lecturer, Department of Guidance and Counseling, Universitas Negeri Malang, Malang, Indonesia. Her research focuses on guidance and counseling based on local wisdom dan cognitive behavior counseling. She can be contacted at email: nur.hidayah.fip@um.ac.id.

Trikinasih Handayani is a Senior Assistant Professor and Lecturer in Teacher Professional Education at Universitas Ahmad Dahlan. She was appointed as a lecturer at the university in 1991 and continued his postgraduate studies in education at Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia. She was appointed a Senior Lecturer in 2009 and an Assistant Senior Professor in 2023. She is passionate about improving students' teaching and learning quality and their development in schools and higher education settings. Dr Hadayani's research interests lie in teacher and teacher education, biology education, higher education, 21st-century teaching and learning, school-based assessment, and classroom research. She can be contacted via email: trikinasih@pbio.uad.ac.id.

Agus Supriyanto is a Lector and Educator in the Guidance and Counselling Study Program at Universitas Ahmad Dahlan. He was appointed a lecturer at the university in 2015 and continued her postgraduate studies in Guidance and Counseling Education at the State University of Semarang, Indonesia. He is passionate about improving the quality of teaching and counselling services to students and development in schools, outside of schools, and in higher education settings. Supriyanto's research interests lie in counselling, psychology, higher education, Islamic counselling, technology in guidance and counselling services, and addiction counselling. He can be contacted via email: agus.supriyanto@bk.uad.ac.id.

Agungbudiprabowo is a Dr. Candidate, Department of Guidance and Counseling, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, Indonesia; and Lecturer, Department of Guidance and Counseling, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Indonesia. His research focuses on career strategy of guidance and counseling intervention. He can be contacted at email: agungbudiprabowo@bk.uad.ac.id.